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Capital Expenditure, Money Supply On Foreign Direct Investment In Nigeria: An Econometric View

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of capital expenditure, money supply and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. In the course of this study, it was discovered that the variables mentioned above leads to economic development which is necessary for the Nigerian economy as a developing economy. But is also involves controlling of ownership in another country. We further discovered that all the variables are integrated of the first order. Furthermore, there was no serial correlation in data. Above all, the variables applied in this study have positive relationships.

Keywords: Expenditure, entity, assets, investments, expanding, money supply, operations.

INTRODUCTION

Capital expenditure is the money that an entity spends to buy, maintain or improve her fixed assets which is achieved through increase in government expenditure with the aim of improving the living standard of her citizens. Capital expenditure also expands any nation's economic base. While Hayes (2017) asserted that capital expenditure is the payment made by the government for providing basic assets which includes property, fixtures or machinery.

An increase in government expenditure will also lead to increase in economic activities (Ali, 2014). But Anyanwu, (2017) posited that capital expenditure deals with accruing physical or tangible goods and as such, capital expenditure will accelerate economic growth. But money supply is regarded as the total value of money available in the economy at a given point in time, this will include currency in circulation and demand deposit (Donaldson, 2003). Currency in circulation is made up coins and notes while demand deposits are considered as those obligations which are not associated with interest payments (BOG, 2015).

Foreign direct investment is considered an investment which is in the form of a controlling ownership in one country by another entity that is based in another country. The investment may be made either by buying an organization in a target country or by expanding the operations of an existing business in that country to a large extent, FDI has become a cornerstone for both governments and corporations (Moosa, 2002). This position is further accepted by Letto (2005) (Buckley, 2011).

The Nigerian Economy is considered as a growing economy and an emerging market. This is because the economy is viewed to be expanding in the following areas such as manufacturing, financial services, technology and entertainment sectors. Towards this backup, the objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of capital expenditure and money supply on foreign direct investment.

Review Of Related Literature

Over the years, Nigeria has spent more money with the aim of stimulating the economy. This is because increased expenditure is considered as the basis for expanding the economy. (Friedman, 2017). Such increase in expenditure also increases government activities. While Lipsey, Richard, Chystal (2011) asserted that increase in government spending results in economic growth. This growth brings about increase in expenditure. And as such capital expenditure is concerned with expenditure in tangible goods such as building, infrastructures and others. (Darma, 2014). Furthermore, capital expenditure is considered to be an expenditure that is always consumed over the useful life of a given fixed asset.

But posited that capital expenditure is meant to increase the value of a nations assets with the view of improving productivity. While CBN (2011) asserted that capital expenditure is an expenditure on goods that are classified as investment goods. But it is important to note that the fundamental reason behind public expenditure is to provide basic infrastructural facilities. But in the views of Havi and Enu, (2018), he posited since government investment is vital, the government must make provision for its maintenance. While Eminer (2017) asserted that where the government does not intervene in the provision of infrastructure, the economy at large will experience negative or slow growth.

Money supply is regarded as the total amount or value of money available in any economy over a given period of time. Money supply is also considered based on various economic activity that is going on in the country. (Osasohan, 2018). But Ekpo and Umoh, (2018) asserted that, the government can influence money supply through the modification of reserve requirements which the banks must hold against deposits in the bank accounts. Such positions that are embarked upon by the government or the financial regulatory body will either increase or lower overall money supply in the economy.

While foreign direct investment is an investment that involves controlling ownership in a business in one country by an entity based in another country. This has also become imperative for governments and organizations. Organization can acquire new technologies and products or in the alternative existing products through the discovery of new markets coupled with controlling interests in foreign assets.

Foreign direct investment brings about economic development, stimulation, easy international trade, economic boosting and employment, it also aids in development of human capital resources, it also creates tax incentives, it brings about resource transfer and increased productivity. Every economy is built on several factors which includes heavy industries, manufacturing, production, technology, financial institutions and tourism. But the Nigerian economy is dominated by crude oil although, it is considered as a mixed economy.

Since public capital expenditure is basically on providing infrastructural facilities, such facilities are designed in such a way that it will make it possible for foreign investors to carry on and investment in the economy at an affordable cost. Furthermore, such investment in capital expenditure will also create jobs. In the views of Gatawa, Adulgafar and Olarinde (2017), they observed that spending on infrastructural facilities, it will increase productivity of investment which will further stimulate FDI flows. Furthermore, FDI has financial viable spillover effect on any economy because it is considered as an indicator of determining economic growth enhancement in a given nation. Money supply has been given various attention in which indicates that there is a strong relationship between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria. In the views of Havi and Enu (2018) they held the view that money supply is an important determining of economic growth. And as such foreign investors are always attracted by the level of investment by the government on infrastructural facilities towards this backdrop, money supply is considered as an economic variable which also affects foreign direct investment.

It also depends heavily on imported goods. But there is a rapid growth in transportation, construction, manufacturing and the entertainment industry. The economy can also be enhanced by investing more in infrastructure, improved educational programmes, liberalizing trade and the efficient allocation of factors of production.

Since Gross domestic product is the total monetary value of all finished goods and services produced within a country, it is considered as a comprehensive score and of a nation's economic health GDP is also used by economist and investors to obtain information and insights on various aspects of the economy.

Based on this, foreign investors can also apply this as a guide for business strategy. The government also applies GDP on what type of monetary policies they are going to implement. GDP will be applied as proxy for the Nigerian economy.

METHODS

Model Specification

This study adopted econometric method of data analysis using secondary data obtained from CBN’s statistical bulletin. The study covered a period of 41 years. The model for this study is

$$GDP = F(CAPEX, MS, FDI)$$

This is further transformed by applying logarithm which is now stated as

$$\text{Log (GDP)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log CAPEX}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{log MS}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{log FDI}_{it} + \Sigma \text{IT}$$

Where Log GDP = Log of gross domestic product

Log CAPEX_{it} = log of capital expenditure

Log MS = log of money supply

Log FDI = log of foreign direct investment

Σit = Error term

β₀ = Constant term

β₁, β₂, β₃, estimated parameters

METHODOLOGY

Our dataset has time series structure comprising yearly observations on capital expenditure (CAPEX), money supply (MS), foreign direct investment (FDI), and gross domestic debt (GDP). The data on these macroeconomic variables are all sourced from the CI3N statistical bulletin, while the analysis was carried out applying EViews version 10. Consistent with previous studies, all data were log-transformed for quality analytical outcome.

Table I shows the summary statistics for the variables, while Figure I shows the time series plots of the data.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera (P-value)
GDP	64070.27	212211.10	5.65	34.23	0.0000
CAPEX	473.99	528.30	1.41	5.03	0.0001
MS	6621.72	9889.04	1.44	3.79	0.0007
FDI	3231.43	5654.26	3.15	13.87	0.0000

Figure 1: Time series plots of log GDP, log CAPEX, log MS, and log FDI.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Stationarity Tests

Table 2 shows the ADF non-stationary test results for the study variables. Both level and first different tests are reported. The lag determination is based on Schwarz information criterion (SIC).

Table 2: ADF nonstationarity tests; parenthesis contains probability values

Variable	Level Test	First Difference Test	Remark
LGDP	-0.8955 (0.7782)	-8.2461 (0.0000)	I(1)
LCAPEX	-0.7734 (0.8152)	-6.3238 (0.0000)	I(1)
LMS	-0.3701 (0.9042)	-37.130 (0.0000)	I(1)
LFDI	-2.2435 (0.1950)	-7.3809 (0.0000)	I(1)

From Table 2, the p-values show that none of our tests on the level series is significant, while all the tests on the first difference series are highly statistically significant. This implies that our variables: namely LGDP, LCAPEX, LMS, and LFDI, are all integrated of the first order or I(1). This implies that both

long-run and short relationships among the study variables can be captured within the ARDL framework, since this framework does not discriminate variables on the basis of their order of integration.

Estimation and Results

Table 3 reports the empirical estimates for the impact of capital expenditure, money supply, and foreign direct investment on gross domestic product. We use the Schwarz information criterion to determine the optimal specification of our empirical model and results show that an ARDL (1,0,0,0) as the best description of the specified relationships (see Figure 2). Further, we follow the HAC error procedure, which produces consistent and robust standard errors even when both serial correlation and heteroskedasticity are present in the data.

Figure 2: SIC Model Selection Criterion

Table 3: Estimated Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	P-value
Intercept	4.0461	0.0001
LGDP(-1)	-0.3210	0.1392
LCAPEX	0.0273	0.8992
LMS	1.1915	0.0004
LFDI	-0.1064	0.2611
CointEq (-1)	-1.3210	0.0000
R-Squared	0.8989	
Adj. R-squared	0.8867	
F-statistic	73.414	0.0000
Durbin-Watson	2.0849	

From Table 3, the results show that the estimated GDP model is highly fitted, (Adj. R-squared = 0.8867) with the combined effect of CAPEX, money supply, and FDI accounting for almost 90% of the observed variation in GDP. Also, the F-statistic (p-value = 0.0000) indicates that the fitted GDP model is highly statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson statistic (DW = 2.0849) is approximately 2, which is ideal value, showing that the model has no serial correlation in the data although, this specification problem has already been controlled since our estimation is based on Newey-West HAC standard errors.

Further, the results show that our specified dynamic relationships have a significant long-run dimension, with the error correction term (CointEq: beta = -1.3210, p-value = 0.0000) having the expected negative sign and is highly statistically significant. The estimated coefficient implies that it takes about 1.3 years for GDP to move back to its equilibrium path with CAPEX, money supply, and FDI after moving away from it due to short-run disturbances. Hence, the speed of adjustment towards the long-run equilibrium path is relatively high.

Our results also indicate that GDP is negatively but not significantly related to its lagged value. The lagged GDP coefficient is estimated at -0.3210 with a p-value of 0.1392, showing that a 1% increase in GDP in the current period would lead to a marginal reduction in GDP by approximately 0.3% one period after, other explaining factors remaining unchanged.

Capital Expenditure and GDP

Our results show that capital expenditure has a positive but not statistically significant relationship with GDP. The coefficient on LCAPEX has an estimated value of 0.0273 with a probability value of 0.8990, indicating that ceteris paribus, an increase in capital expenditure by 1% would, on average, lead to a marginal or inappreciable increase in GDP by approximately 0.03%.

Hence, the effect of capital expenditure on GDP is not also significant in economic sense. This result shows that fiscal policy through changes in government's capital expenditure is not an effective instrument for long-run growth in Nigeria. Although, the positive sign of the CAPEX beta is consistent with the theoretical prediction, our result, however, contradicts the fiscal policy argument that government can deliberately archive higher long-run growth by adjusting its expenditure and other fiscal variables.

Money supply and GDP

Our results show that money supply has a positive and highly statistically significant relationship with GDP. The coefficient on LMS is estimated at 1.1915 with a p-value of 0.0004, indicating that ceteris paribus, an increase in money supply by 1% would, on average, lead to an appreciable increase in GDP by approximately 1.2%.

Hence, the effect of money supply on GDP is also significant in economic sense. This result shows that unlike fiscal policy, monetary policy through changes in money supply can serve as an effective instrument for achieving long-run growth in Nigeria. The positive sign of the MS beta is also consistent with the theoretical prediction as well as agrees with several previous studies across the globe.

Foreign Direct Investment and GDP

Our results show that foreign direct investment has a negative but not statistically significant relationship with GDP. The coefficient on LFDI is estimated at -0.1064 with a p-value of 0.2611, indicating that ceteris paribus, an increase in foreign direct investment by 1% would, on average, lead to a decrease in GDP by approximately 0.1%. Hence, like CAPEX, the effect of foreign direct investment on GDP is not economically significant. This result has, therefore, revealed the tendency for foreign direct investment to reduce or deter long-run economic growth in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the impact of three macroeconomic variables: namely, capital expenditure, money supply, and foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria using the ARDL model. The analysis is based on time series data collected at yearly frequency from 1981 to 2020. Our results, which is based on a model that controls for both serial correlation and heteroskedasticity problems, lead to the following main conclusions.

The relationship between capital expenditure and GDP is positive but not statistically significant. Hence, our data do not provide empirical evidence to support the well-established theoretical view that fiscal policy through changes in government capital expenditure is an effective instrument for achieving long-run economic growth. Our econometric analysis shows that money supply has a positive effect on economic growth. Hence, consistent with monetary policy theory, we conclude that changes in the quantity and availability of money can effectively drive long-run economic growth in Nigeria.

We find that the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth is negative but not statistically significant.

RECOMMENDATION

The study viewed the effect of capital expenditure and money supply on foreign direct investment as a major source of improving the standard of living of the masses and as such the study recommends that since money supply is positive, capital expenditure so be expended in such a manner it will aid investors to come into your nation and invest. Furthermore, for foreigners to invest in the economy, certain tax incentive should be extended to certain areas of the economy. Capital expenditure should be considered in areas that are seen to bring about increase in development and growth.

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